

AI-Driven Orchestration of 6G-Enabled Services Across the Computing Continuum

Grigorios Kakkavas*, Ioannis Tzanettis*, Alexandros Stylos*, Ignacio Labrador Pavón†, Enrique Lluesma Martí†, Adam Zahir‡, Constantine Ayimba‡, Nassima Toumi§, Belma Turkovic§, Anastasios Zafeiropoulos* and Symeon Papavassiliou*

*Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece
e-mails: {gkakkavas, gtzanettis, alstylos}@netmode.ntua.gr, tzafeir@cn.ntua.gr, papavass@mail.ntua.gr

†Research and Innovation Department, ATOS, Madrid, Spain
e-mails: {ignacio.labrador, enrique.lluesma}@eviden.com

‡Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Madrid, Spain
e-mails: azahir@pa.uc3m.es, ayconsta@it.uc3m.es

§Networks, TNO, The Hague, Netherlands

e-mails: {nassima.toumi, belma.turkovic}@tno.nl

Abstract—The emergence of 6G mobile communications promises transformative advancements powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). However, these capabilities introduce significant challenges, mainly due to the heterogeneous nature of 6G-enabled environments. This paper presents an AI-driven orchestration framework designed to address the complexities of future 6G infrastructures. The proposed framework orchestrates microservice-based applications across diverse layers of the computing continuum and performs key tasks such as service placement, computation offloading, horizontal scaling, and live migration, leveraging AI to enhance performance, energy efficiency, and automation. Additionally, it incorporates Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to enable federated service management when centralized control is impractical. We validate this approach through experimental trials with a latency-sensitive 6G application, analyzing intra- and inter-domain orchestration, proactive extreme edge migration, and inter-cluster communication technologies. A set of representative workflows are provided as open-source implementations.

Index Terms—6G networks, computing continuum, service orchestration, AI-assisted orchestration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of 6G mobile communications promises unprecedented advancements in data transmission speeds, latency reduction, and connectivity for an increasingly digital world, with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) playing a critical role in enhancing these capabilities [1]. AI will enable more intelligent and efficient network management, allowing networks to autonomously adapt to changing conditions in real time. However, these advanced capabilities come with significant challenges, primarily due to the heterogeneous nature of 6G environments. The computing continuum in a 6G ecosystem spans multiple layers, ranging from the clouds and core networks of individual stakeholders, which may host centralized data centers, to the extreme edge that extends beyond the stakeholders' own edge domains [2]. Each

of these layers has distinct characteristics and computational power. Efficiently managing resources and ensuring seamless service delivery across them requires innovative approaches that can dynamically adapt to the real-time demands of applications while considering the constraints of network capacity, energy efficiency, and system reliability. Traditional management techniques, which rely on static and centralized models, will no longer suffice. Instead, more advanced distributed and synergetic orchestration strategies are necessary, particularly those incorporating AI-driven solutions.

Microservices architecture (MSA) has emerged as a response to the growing need for scalable and flexible software applications. Microservice-based applications decompose a complex system into small, autonomous services, each focused on a specific business function, enabling independent development and management [3]. Orchestration in this context involves managing the deployment, scalability, and coordination of these microservices across diverse and dynamic environments [4]. Towards this goal, several specific orchestration tasks arise across the computing continuum. Representative examples include service placement, computation offloading, scaling (either vertical or horizontal), and migration. Moreover, such distributed 6G-enabled applications (i.e., distributed applications that leverage advanced 6G features) incorporate diverse interconnected chains of microservices, each with unique requirements and operational needs. Consequently, a single, uniform orchestration mechanism cannot effectively manage all of them. Instead, an orchestration framework must adopt a modular approach, comprising various specialized modules tailored to different application service chains. On a case-by-case basis, the appropriate module should manage the specific service chain based on its unique characteristics and requirements.

In this paper, we present a comprehensive orchestration approach designed to manage 6G-enabled services across the computing continuum. The proposed framework integrates AI-driven mechanisms to enhance energy efficiency, meet

This work has been partly funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS project Hexa-X-II (Grant Agreement no. 101095759).

stringent latency requirements, and enable forecasting-based orchestration. It supports deployments across multiple clusters and extreme edge infrastructure, leveraging Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to facilitate federated service management when centralized control of resources is not possible. Representative workflows supported by the framework are provided as open source implementations. The framework's performance is evaluated through realistic experimental trials, utilizing an open-source, latency-sensitive distributed 6G application developed specifically for testing together with an infrastructure emulator that models the features of the envisaged future 6G networks. The experiments examine intra- and inter-domain orchestration, extreme edge migration, and network service mesh configurations, with results demonstrating the framework's capability for efficient, resilient orchestration in latency-critical, high-availability microservice-based applications within distributed 6G infrastructures.

II. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

A. AI-enabled orchestration

1) *Multi-agent orchestration*: A mechanism for modeling and evaluating Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) algorithms is proposed to tackle concurrent scaling and migration of services in multi-cluster setups. The deployed agents act as representatives of different actors with different objectives and responsibilities using variable utility functions and communication methods [5] to take efficient actions. In the considered scenario in this work, agents need to select a suitable (with regard to performance/cost trade-offs) number of replicas to handle incoming workloads, while the multi-cluster setup introduces a complexity regarding the services proximity to the source of the requests. The agents interact with the multi-cluster environment to obtain state information (e.g., latency, CPU usage, memory, request rate) from observability tools and to initiate scaling and migration actions.

2) *Energy-efficient orchestration*: The proposed orchestration solution aims to perform service placement and migration that satisfies specific service key performance indicators (KPIs) while minimizing energy consumption. To do this, when selecting the target node for the placement or migration of a service, the proposed model uses energy related information as input such as the energy source for the node (e.g., green or fossil energy), the battery level for extreme edge nodes, or the amount of consumed resources to encourage consolidating services on a smaller set of physical nodes. Additionally, a decentralized approach is adopted, where a separate AI/ML model supports orchestration decisions for each service, thereby minimizing computation and energy consumption of the AI/ML model by considering a smaller set of states and actions. Furthermore, multiple model versions can be trained to satisfy the specific requirements and KPIs of different service types and quality of experience (QoE) levels.

3) *Forecasting-based orchestration*: A key challenge for future 6G networks is integrating the extreme edge domain to manage and orchestrate network services across the entire network continuum. This extreme edge includes diverse, cloud-

native infrastructure from multiple stakeholders, with volatile and error-prone resources that may abruptly and unexpectedly change their availability status and capabilities. AI/ML is considered a key enabler for the extreme edge integration, helping to forecast user behaviors and network events by analyzing the large diverse data sets and KPIs in this domain. This allows for triggering proactive management and orchestration actions, such as migrating, scaling, or reconfiguring service components when infrastructure changes are anticipated.

B. Deployment in the computing continuum

1) *Inter-Cluster Communication for Distributed Deployments*: To facilitate the orchestration of workloads using AI/ML algorithms, network connections cross-cluster must be automatically created or updated upon their deployment or removal. For intra-cluster communication, this problem is addressed by the different Container Network Interface (CNI) implementations and by using abstractions, such as Kubernetes Services, which act as load balancers over a set of pods. However, in the case of inter-cluster communication, similar solutions are not directly applicable, and new approaches are needed. Therefore, over the last few years, multiple available options enabling this, such as Network Service Mesh (NSM)¹ and Karmada²/Submariner³, have been developed. NSM is a Hybrid/Multi-cloud IP Service Mesh that, by working in parallel with the existing CNIs, connects workloads running in multiple clusters. Karmada on the other hand enables seamless communication between multiple Kubernetes clusters by integrating with Submariner, which establishes secure network connectivity across clusters.

2) *Virtualized Extreme Edge Infrastructure*: Experimentation in extreme-edge domains can get notably difficult due to its heterogeneous nature, introducing massive numbers of nodes and highly volatile and unpredictable behavior, with nodes attaching/detaching from the network in an asynchronous way. A tool enabling the emulation of the extreme edge domain with its main relevant features would greatly contribute to the realization of various meaningful experiments. Access to a virtualized extreme edge infrastructure emulating such a domain in a feasible and cost-effective way can offer multiple benefits such as enhanced stress testing as well as scheduling of complex scenarios for evaluation of newly developed orchestration mechanisms. For this purpose, an Infrastructure Layer Emulator (ILE) has been developed based on virtualized container-based technology.

3) *DLT-based Federation*: Federation is a multi-domain concept that allows service providers to orchestrate services or resources from other domains, thereby extending their local capabilities to meet the specific needs of vertical customers. This process requires careful coordination and negotiation among service providers, which is challenging in dynamic environments where quick, short-term federation relationships

¹<https://networkservicemesh.io/>

²<https://karmada.io>

³<https://submariner.io>

Fig. 1. Service orchestration framework overview

are required. Legacy solutions rely on pre-established agreements, making them unsuitable in such dynamic settings given their inadequacy to guarantee security, performance, and scalability [6] on an ad-hoc basis. To address these challenges, the proposed orchestration framework integrates Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), specifically blockchain and Smart-Contracts (SCs) [7]. A permissioned blockchain is employed, where each service provider runs a blockchain node connected to the service orchestrator. Federation procedures are managed by a generic SC, serving as a distributed authority on the blockchain. Service providers interact with the SC through immutable transactions recorded on the ledger.

III. PROPOSED SERVICE ORCHESTRATION FRAMEWORK

The design and internal architecture of the proposed framework is illustrated in Fig. 1. The framework's operation starts with the service provider registering the application's requirements and constraints. The orchestrator then formulates an initial deployment plan, guiding the multi-cluster manager to allocate microservices optimally across various clusters. Moreover, it maps the application's service chains to suitable modules, implementing the appropriate orchestration mechanisms for efficient management. The framework supports continuous service lifecycle management, including real-time monitoring and orchestration actions, through a closed loop that adapts decisions based on observed performance metrics. Finally, when deployment spans multiple administrative domains, the framework facilitates service federation via a DLT mechanism to ensure seamless integration and coordination.

A. Framework components

The components described here are designed to encompass the functionalities necessary for making decisions, deploying services, and monitoring deployments within a single domain, while also enabling inter-domain communication.

1) *Application Descriptor*: This component provides an interface for the service provider to describe the services for deployment and their corresponding specifications, such as scalability, privacy concerns, and optimization criteria. A descriptive language is necessary to express the services' computation and communication requirements. Therefore, to describe

the application used for experimentation in Section IV, the application graph model is proposed as explained in [8]. This description was selected because it effectively captures the requirements of highly distributed applications, including its connectivity specifications and constraints regarding specific services or workflows.

2) *Infrastructure*: The infrastructure discussed in the context of a specific domain regards both network and computing resources. These include not only physical and virtual resources but also emulated elements provided by the Infrastructure Layer Emulator (ILE) described in Section IV-B3.

3) *Deployment Manager*: The Deployment Manager supports single-cluster as well as multi-cluster service interconnectivity. The technologies adopted in this component tackle the issue of connecting distributed clusters into a single domain, moving responsibility to a centralized point, allowing complex deployment schemes to occur by decoupling interconnectivity issues from the decision-making process. Moreover, this component is responsible for applying orchestration actions to the infrastructure, such as scaling and migration actions, application deployment, and load balancing rules.

4) *Orchestrator*: This component encompasses the orchestration intelligence responsible for any decision-making related to service deployment. The orchestrator's objectives include meeting the service-level agreements (SLAs) of registered services, optimizing key performance metrics, evaluating incoming service federation requests, and maintaining application workflows across domains. This multi-objective role demands sophisticated decision-making, for which the AI-driven techniques discussed in Section II-A are employed.

5) *Monitoring and Telemetry*: Information on service deployments is collected by gathering data from both the services themselves as well as the resources they consume. Additionally, federated services require closer and more intricate monitoring to ensure compliance with their respective SLAs. Observability plays a crucial role in modern service deployment systems [9], where multiple data types (such as metrics, traces, and logs) are essential for effectively managing the deployment life cycle.

6) *Federation Manager*: A DLT-based component enabling dynamic negotiation and execution of service federation. It facilitates efficient service deployment across multiple domains by leveraging SCs. This functionality is crucial for ensuring service continuity in dynamic scenarios.

B. Framework workflows

1) *Multi-cluster orchestration*: In the multi-cluster setup, a single operator may hold the responsibility to manage service deployment across multiple clusters, but the individual cluster operators may also deploy their own orchestration agents for consuming local resources. This workflow takes advantage of the proposed framework to setup different agent networks that collaboratively or independently try to optimally handle their given tasks based on their specific objectives. It exploits the *Application Descriptor* to identify the relevant KPIs and utilizes the *Multi-agent orchestration* mechanism of the

Orchestrator and the service deployment capabilities of the *Deployment Manager* to deploy the service chain on top of the multi-cluster infrastructure. The *Monitoring Framework* is used for the real-time observation of the services' deployment during training of the agents and during evaluation of the management lifecycle.

2) *DLT-based service federation*: Each new domain joining the blockchain gains access to the blockchain network by deploying and connecting a local blockchain node. It then registers on the SC through a single transaction using its unique blockchain address, which includes the domain's information and service footprint. The federation process starts when the consumer domain sends a service announcement transaction to the SC, specifying the requirements for the desired service. Potential provider domains listening for federation events receive the service announcement and respond by issuing transactions containing their bid-offers (service prices) in a reverse-auction format. The consumer domain evaluates all offers and selects the most suitable provider based on the bids and internal policies. The selected provider domain deploys the requested federated service and confirms the deployment with a transaction containing the service details. The SC records the successful deployment and initiates charging for the federated service. Finally, the consumer receives the deployment confirmation, and both domains establish data plane connectivity.

3) *Services migration on the extreme edge*: For services that are deployed on extreme edge devices, it is necessary to take into account the availability of the devices to ensure service continuity. Thus, an orchestration decision module is needed to migrate services between extreme edge devices based on the collected or predicted availability data for the devices, as well as additional service-specific constraints such as resource capacity, link latency or energy aspects. To this end, the orchestrator periodically receives status information about the extreme edge infrastructure, and determines whether service instances need to be migrated based on the observed or predicted availability of the extreme edge devices where they have been deployed. Then, for the set of identified service instances, the orchestrator determines the migration targets for each service and triggers the migration process.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Microservice-based Application

To demonstrate and evaluate the proposed orchestration framework, an open-source smart manufacturing application for managing the operation of a static robotic arm was developed⁴. It is composed of two main service chains, one regarding the teleoperation of a robot vehicle surveilling the workspace of the arm and a second regarding the generation of alerts to safely pause and start the operation based on an ML-based object detection component analyzing the video stream of the vehicle. The object detection service chain comprises two main components: the frame sampler, which samples the frames from the stream with a configurable

⁴<https://gitlab.com/netmode/6g-latency-sensitive-service>

Fig. 2. Multi-cluster testbed layout

Fig. 3. Federated testbed layout

sampling rate, and the object detector, which analyzes the frames and generates alerts in an emergency. The second application service chain comprises three essential components: the encoder, responsible for encoding frames before forwarding the stream; the media server, handling the received stream for distribution and management; and the front end, serving as the user interface for accessing and interacting with the vehicle.

B. Experimentation testbed

1) *Multi-cluster management*: The experimental scenarios are executed on a two-cluster virtualized testbed, illustrated in Fig. 2. The setup is implemented on two Intel Xeon Silver 4110 bare-metal servers supporting a set of virtual nodes on which a Kubernetes cluster with substantial resources (2 nodes - 16 vCPUs, 16 GiB of RAM) representing the Cloud environment and a K3s cluster with limited resources (1 node - 4 vCPUs, 8 GiB of RAM) representing the Edge environment are deployed. The OpenTelemetry⁵ framework is used for collecting observational data and an *Observability Server* (instantiating the Monitoring Framework) supports storage and real-time access to the data by the intelligent mechanisms.

2) *Federated testbed*: The multi-domain federation environment is established as shown in Fig. 3. It comprises two independent domains, each featuring a Kubernetes cluster implemented with the MicroK8s⁶ distribution and managed by a custom-built orchestrator. To provide the autonomous federation of the object detection service leveraging the SC trigger, each domain is also equipped with a containerized Ethereum-based blockchain node integrated with its orchestrator, forming a peer-to-peer blockchain network. Access to the SC is facilitated through a REST API for seamless interoperability. In

⁵<https://opentelemetry.io>

⁶<https://microk8s.io/>

Fig. 4. JSM - ISM - MSM performance comparison

order to ensure separation between domains, they are isolated in virtual machines as illustrated in the figure.

3) *Infrastructure Layer Emulator (ILE)*: This component emulates the key features of the infrastructure envisaged for the future 6G networks, focusing on targeting the challenges related to extreme edge integration (presented as the Extreme edge cluster in Fig. 2). The ILE is built on LXD⁷, a container and virtual machine manager that runs full Linux systems in containers or virtual machines. It supports a wide range of Linux distributions, from lightweight options for deploying many nodes on limited hardware to full distributions capable of running complex network services. LXD can scale from a single instance to a cluster simulating a full data center, making it ideal for a variety of scenarios. The ILE has been made available under the Apache 2.0 Open Source license⁸.

C. Methodology and Results

1) *Multi-cluster service orchestration*: The ML-based object detector component is selected to be horizontally scaled as required based on the measured workload and end-to-end latency, being migrated from the edge to the cloud and vice-versa. A two-layer orchestration strategy is applied that delegates responsibilities from top-layer systems to lower-layer ones, simplifying the management of distributed deployments. The mechanism is implemented using a MARL methodology where each agent tackles a different task: agent 1 migrates the service across clusters and agent 2 handles the scaling factor of the service. The multi-agent mechanism is compared with a centralized, RL-based, joint autoscaling-placement mechanism [10] managing the application. The orchestration actions of both setups are decided based on the evaluation computation and communication delays collected at specific monitoring points. The autoscaling and placement mechanisms evaluate the collected data, and for every interval, the agents select where the optimal placement is and how many replicas are needed for guaranteeing SLOs satisfaction.

Three different agent setups are used to demonstrate how different domain synergies can influence SLA satisfaction: i) Joint Scaling-Migration (JSM), ii) Independent Scaling-Migration (ISM), iii) Mixed Scaling-Migration (MSM). The

state in all cases considers request arrival rate, replica number and placement for each of the deployed services. JSM assumes a central DQN agent taking joint scaling (1-3 replicas) and migration (edge/cloud) decisions. Thus, the underlying network of DQN with 1 hidden layer is of size $6 \times 64 \times 6$. ISM assumes independent scaling and migration by two DQN agents, thus the two networks are of sizes $6 \times 64 \times 3$ and $6 \times 64 \times 2$. MSM tries a hybrid approach where agents act independently but consider global rewards as feedback adopting the QMIX [11] methodology. The agent networks are similar with ISM and the mixing network used for training is a 2-layered network. The first layer has a size 2×64 for the weights, generated by a hypernetwork of size 6×128 . The second layer has a size 64×1 for the weights, generated by a hypernetwork of size 6×64 . Biases for both layers are also generated by the hypernetworks of sizes 6×64 and 6×1 , respectively.

Three main metrics are used for the evaluation, the percentage of requests that violate the SLA (i.e., the latency threshold), the utilization of the link (LU) between the two clusters, and the resource consumption (RC) in terms of percentage of used replicas. The reward function for JSM and MSM is calculated as a weighted average of the three metrics (SLA,LU,RC) showcasing the objective difference from ISM which calculates the rewards separately for the agents based on their own objectives, i.e., (SLA,LU) and (SLA,RC) respectively. The results are illustrated in Fig. 4 where the evaluation metrics are depicted for the three different setups.

JSM meets the SLA requirements for both low (1 frame/sec) and high (10 frames/sec) workloads. However, this comes at the cost of high link utilization and medium to high resource consumption. On the other hand, ISM demonstrates minimal link utilization and resource consumption but fails to satisfy SLA requirements for high workloads, as its agents operate independently. MSM, in contrast to ISM, introduces collaboration between agents, reducing SLA violations but increasing link utilization and resource consumption, even for low workloads (1 frame/sec). The comparison between ISM and MSM highlights how introducing collaboration directives can enable agents operating in a decentralized manner to achieve global objectives, albeit with higher resource costs. Furthermore, while JSM outperforms MSM in this relatively simple setup with only two orchestration tasks, MSM's advantage lies in its ability to scale more effectively to complex scenarios. Finally, centralized solutions like JSM may not always be feasible when multiple stakeholders are involved.

2) *Inter-domain DLT-based service orchestration*: As illustrated in Fig. 3, the experimental scenario consists of two domains: a consumer and a provider. Both domains are pre-registered in the SC with their unique blockchain addresses, and the consumer domain is initially running the microservice-based application detailed in Section IV-A. A resource saturation event is simulated in the consumer's edge infrastructure, affecting the object detection module due to its high computational requirements. In response, the consumer domain (via the orchestrator) autonomously triggers the federation process through the SC, requesting the migration of the

⁷<https://canonical.com/lxd>

⁸<https://gitlab.com/decentralized-continuum-orchestration/infrastructure-layer-emulator>

Fig. 5. Federation times breakdown

object detection module. The consumer and provider domains negotiate federation terms using the reverse-auction mechanism described in Section III-B, leading to a dynamic SLA agreement. The provider then deploys the requested service, configuring a Kubernetes load balancer to provide external network access for the consumer. Upon successful deployment, the consumer domain receives the connection details from the SC, terminates its local object detection module, and redirects the incoming video stream to the federated service hosted by the provider domain, without any service downtime.

Fig. 5 presents the average accumulated times for each procedure in the federation process, which is completed in approximately 15 seconds. Specifically, it takes 2.93 seconds for the consumer to send a service announcement requesting federation, 3.80 seconds for the provider to respond with a bid offer, 3.99 seconds for the consumer to select and notify the provider, 0.75 seconds for the provider to deploy the federated service (including load balancer setup), and 3.25 seconds for final deployment confirmation, connectivity details sharing, and consumer integration into the end-to-end service.

3) *High-availability extreme edge migration*: Node availability forecasting experiments were conducted using the ILE, emulating a testbed infrastructure layer with 35 Linux nodes. Ten nodes represented a specific stakeholder (a network operator), while the remaining 25 simulated the network’s extreme edge domain. To replicate extreme edge volatility, these 25 nodes were set to be pseudo-randomly switched on/off without warning. On that infrastructure, the described latency-sensitive 6G service was deployed, in such a way that some of its components (those in charge of processing the video streams) were deployed on volatile nodes of the extreme edge, i.e., on those nodes that could asynchronously connect/disconnect.

For the forecasting functionality, a machine learning model was developed, featuring a single feed-forward neural network with two distinct input pathways. This design has been chosen to enhance modularity and effectively handle the heterogeneous nature of data input: time data (size $2 \times 64 \times 64 \times 64$) and network infrastructure state data (size $25 \times 32 \times 32$). Both pathways are concatenated in the last hidden layer of the network resulting in a combined layer of size $(64 + 32) \times 96 \times 25$. The model was trained with a dataset of historical information on the infrastructure nodes availability obtained during an emulation period equivalent to one week.

Once trained, the model was used to trigger migration actions on the service components that could be running on nodes that were predicted to go offline within a short period

of time, to ensure the service continuity with high availability. More specifically, the proactive migration mechanism was implemented relying on the K8s ‘taint’ command, to restrict workloads on those nodes envisaged to be disconnected in the prediction time span. Based on this, even in such a volatile setup, the service was kept running without disruptions during the emulation. Considering that predictions are obtained every 30 seconds and the network service migration time ranges from 4 to 6 seconds, no service loss was observed. Consequently, video streaming remained smooth and uninterrupted.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented an AI-driven orchestration framework tailored to meet the complex demands of 6G-enabled services across the computing continuum. By integrating artificial intelligence, DLT, emulation tools, and multi-cluster communication, the framework enables efficient, resilient, and adaptive management of microservice-based applications focusing on energy efficiency and high availability. Experimental validation using a latency-sensitive 6G application yielded promising results, demonstrating the framework’s flexibility in optimizing service placement, computation offloading, and live migration across distributed infrastructures.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Alhammedi, I. Shayea, A. A. El-Saleh, M. H. Azmi, Z. H. Ismail, L. Kouhalvandi, and S. A. Saad, “Artificial Intelligence in 6G Wireless Networks: Opportunities, Applications, and Challenges,” *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, vol. 2024, pp. 1–27, Mar. 2024.
- [2] A. Al-Dulaimy, M. Jansen, B. Johansson, A. Trivedi, A. Iosup, M. Ashjaei, A. Galletta, D. Kimovski, R. Prodan, K. Tserpes, G. Kousiouris, C. Giannakos, I. Brandic, N. Ali, A. B. Bondi, and A. V. Papadopoulos, “The computing continuum: From IoT to the cloud,” *Internet of Things*, vol. 27, p. 101272, Oct. 2024.
- [3] M. Söylemez, B. Tekinerdogan, and A. Kolukisa Tarhan, “Challenges and Solution Directions of Microservice Architectures: A Systematic Literature Review,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 5507, May 2022.
- [4] N. F. Saraiva De Sousa, D. A. Lachos Perez, R. V. Rosa, M. A. Santos, and C. Esteve Rothenberg, “Network Service Orchestration: A survey,” *Computer Communications*, vol. 142–143, pp. 69–94, Jun. 2019.
- [5] J. N. Foerster, Y. M. Assael, N. de Freitas, and S. Whiteson, “Learning to communicate with deep multi-agent reinforcement learning,” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1605.06676>
- [6] K. Antevski and C. J. Bernardos, “Federation in Dynamic Environments: Can Blockchain Be the Solution?” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 32–38, Feb. 2022.
- [7] N. Szabo, “The idea of smart contracts,” *Nick Szabo’s Papers and Concise Tutorials*, 1997.
- [8] A. Zafeiropoulos, E. Fotopoulou, C. Vassilakis, I. Tzanettis, C. Lombardo, A. Carrega, and R. Bruschi, “Intent-driven distributed applications management over compute and network resources in the computing continuum,” in *2023 19th International Conference DCOSS-IoT*, 2023, pp. 429–436.
- [9] I. Tzanettis, C.-M. Androna, A. Zafeiropoulos, E. Fotopoulou, and S. Papavassiliou, “Data fusion of observability signals for assisting orchestration of distributed applications,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 5, 2022.
- [10] I. Tzanettis, G. Kakkavas, A. Stylos, A. Zafeiropoulos, and S. Papavassiliou, “A cloud-native approach for orchestrating 6G-enabled services at the computing continuum,” in *2024 IEEE 29th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [11] T. Rashid, M. Samvelyan, C. S. de Witt, G. Farquhar, J. Foerster, and S. Whiteson, “Qmix: Monotonic value function factorisation for deep multi-agent reinforcement learning,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1803.11485>